

Science technology & Digital finance

journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>

ACCOUNTING SYSTEM IN GERMANY

¹Rashidov Abror Ruzimurod ugli, ²Shokirov Shirinbek Dilshod ugli, ³Mahkamov Azamat Ravshan ugli

¹Assistant of the Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan.

^{2,3}Students of the Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan Bachelor of world and regional economics and the joint educational program of the Kazan federal University.

СИСТЕМА БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В ГЕРМАНИИ

¹Рашидов Аброр Рузимурад угли, ²Шокиров Ширинбек Дилшод угли, ³Махкамов Азамат Равшан угли

¹Ассистент Джизакского филиала Национального университета Узбекистана.

^{2,3}Студенты бакалавриата мировой и региональной экономики Джизакского филиала Национального университета Узбекистана и совместной образовательной программы Казанского федерального университета.

GERMANIYADA BUXGALTERIYA TIZIMI

¹Rashidov Abror Ro'zimurod o'g'li, ²Shokirov Shirinbek Dilshod o'g'li, ³Mahkamov Azamat Ravshan o'g'li

¹O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali assistenti.

^{2,3}O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali jahon va mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot bakalavri hamda Qozon federal universitetining qo'shma ta'lim dasturi talabalari.

abstract

This publication discusses the basic principles of accounting in Germany, the legislative framework for accounting, and also describes the accounting systems using simplified and double entry systems.

аннотация

В данной публикации рассматриваются основные принципы бухгалтерского учета в Германии, законодательная база бухгалтерского учета, а также описываются системы бухгалтерского учета с использованием упрощенной системы и системы двойной записи.

annotatsiya

Ushbu nashrda Germaniyada buxgalteriya hisobining asosiy tamoyillari, buxgalteriya hisobining Qonunchilik bazasi muhokama qilinadi, shuningdek soddalashtirilgan va ikki tomonlama

kirish tizimlaridan foydalangan holda buxgalteriya hisobi tizimlari tavsiflanadi.

Keywords:

GoB, functions of accounting, legal rules for accounting, VAT Act, HGB.

Ключевые слова:

GoB, функции бухгалтерского учета, правовые нормы бухгалтерского учета, Закон о НДС, HGB.

Kalit so'zlar:

GoB, buxgalteriya hisobi funktsiyalari, buxgalteriya hisobining huquqiy qoidalari, QQS to'g'risidagi qonun, HGB.

©2023. *Rashidov Abror Ruzimurod ugli, Shokirov Shirinbek Dilshod ugli, Mahkamov Azamat Ravshan ugli.*

Introduction

In Germany, there are two accounting systems: simplified and double entry. When looking at accounting, it is necessary to adhere to the relevant regulations and principles of accounting (GoB).

1. What is accounting?

It should be noted that in Germany there are two terms related to accounting: Buchführung and Buchhaltung. The term Buchführung refers to keeping records of all business transactions. The term Buchhaltung, in turn, usually refers to the department in a company that is responsible for recording business transactions and postings. Thus, the task of Buchführung is to document the financial transactions of the company, while Buchhaltung is the department of the company responsible for maintaining accounting records.

2. Functions of accounting. The main function of accounting is to record all expenses and income. In addition, there are a number of special tasks that are also performed within the framework of accounting: analysis of the enterprise's turnover and monitoring it; ensuring transparency of the ratio of own and borrowed funds; tracking payments made by customers and customer debts; warning of possible insolvency; preparation of reports for subsequent taxation.

3. Legal rules for accounting. There are a number of legal rules that must be followed when maintaining accounting records. Points concerning in what form and why records must be kept, what rules must be observed and what guidelines entrepreneurs must adhere to in the accounting process are contained in the following laws:

Income Tax Law (Einkommensteuergesetz[1]);

VAT Act (Umsatzsteuergesetz[2]);

Publication Law (Publikationsgesetz[3]);

Law on Share Capital (Aktiengesetz[4]);

Law on Limited Liability Companies (GmbH-Gesetz[5]);

Tax legislation (Abgabenordnung[6]).

The obligation of all enterprises to comply with GoB when conducting accounting is defined by §238[7], paragraph 1 of HGB and §264[8] paragraph. 2 positions of 1 HGB. Despite this, there is no single official set of GoB principles. The German Federal Ministry of Finance explains this circumstance as follows: "GoB is an indefinite legal term; the principles of GoB are determined, in particular, by legal norms and case law and must be interpreted and applied individually in each case." (BFH Resolution of May 12, 1966, BStBl III p. 372; Resolution of the BVerfG of October 10, 1961, 2 BvL 1/59, BVerfGE 13 p. 153). GoB can evolve and undergo

changes under the influence of expert opinions, trade customs, business practices, common law, organizational and technical changes. Thus, the GoB principles partially consist of "unwritten laws", a number of which are reflected in regulatory legal acts. Depending on the specific case, they can be interpreted in different ways. Possible gaps in the legislation are not excluded. The basic principles of accounting are set out in §239[9], para. 2 HGB: "Ledger entries and other necessary records must be complete, accurate, timely and orderly."

3.1. The principle of completeness. The principle of completeness (Vollständigkeit) is described in detail in §246[10] HGB, para. 1. This principle implies that all business transactions (expenses and income), assets, debts, liabilities and deferred expenses should be reflected in the financial statements. The completeness principle is considered fulfilled only when all other GoB principles are fulfilled.

3.2. The principle of accuracy and freedom from arbitrariness. The principle of accuracy (Richtigkeit) is observed when the financial statements are compiled in accordance with the current legislation, and all indicators given in the report are clearly monitored and verifiable. The principle of accuracy is complemented by the principle of freedom from arbitrariness (Willkürfreiheit), which implies that, if necessary, the compiler of the accounting report has the right to resort to approximate values, but these approximate values should not create a false impression about the financial situation of the company. **3.3. The principle of clarity and clarity** The principle of clarity (Klarheit) and clarity (Übersichtlichkeit) refers to the external design of accounting books and other documentation. In particular, financial statements should be clear and understandable for the tax administration. The mandatory formal criteria applied to accounting for the preparation of the balance sheet are regulated by §266[11] HGB, the criteria for the preparation of the income statement (EÜR) – in §275[12] HGB. For the notes to the EÜR report, see section 4, paragraph 3 of the Income Tax Act[1] (Einkommenssteuergesetzes – EStG).

3.4. The principle of increasing the book value. The principle of increasing the book value (Wertaufhellung) determines how information that became known after the reporting date (the last day of the financial year) affects the financial statements. An increase in the book value occurs when incoming information, for example, information about a financial transaction, was known before the reporting date, but the reporting on it was not ready on time. In this case, it is allowed to include new information in the financial statements after the fact. The legal basis for the principle of value increase can be found in §252[13] para.1 Resolution No. 4 HGB. **3.5. Accrual principles** The principles of proper accounting also include the so-called accrual

principles (Abgrenzungsgrundsätze). They consist of: the principle of implementation; the principle of impartiality; the principle of caution.

References:

1. Бобаназарова Ж., Рашидов А. Развитие сфер услуг на основе цифровой трансформации экономики //Информатика и инженерные технологии. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 134-136.
2. Rashidov A. BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING TURLARI //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 153-160.
3. Abror R., Shahobiddin K. MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISH VA YUQORI IQTISODIY O 'SISH SUR'ATLARINI TA'MINLASHNING USTUVOR YO 'NALISHLARI //INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 35. – С. 327-331.
4. Abror Ro'zimurod o'g R. et al. THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING THE INCOME OF THE POPULATION AND IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY //Academia Science Repository. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 5. – С. 710-714.
5. Abror Ro'zimurod o'g R. et al. INSON KAPITALINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH HAMDA AHOLI TURMUSH DARAJASINI YAXSHILASH //INTERDISCIPLINE INNOVATION AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 9-11.
6. Abror Ro'zimurod o'g R. et al. JIZZAX VILOYATI IQTISODIY O'SISH KO'RSATKICHLARI YOKI JARAYONLARI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 20-22.
7. Ismailova, Nilufar Sabitjanovna, Uchqun Ro'Zimurod O'G'Li, and Abror Ro'Zimurod O'G'Li. "JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA QO'SHILISH: QO'SHILISH JARAYONI HAMDA UNING QONUNIY ASOSLARI." Scientific progress 2.2 (2021): 1095-1098.
8. Rashidov U., Rashidov A., Naimov S. Modern Views on the Problems of Management Accounting in Logistics System // "ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2022. – С. 276-283.
9. Rashidov U., Rashidov A. Assessment of Costs For the Quality of Logistics Activities //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 39-43.
10. Rashidov A., Leonodovna M. N., Azlarkhan A. The importance of financial accounting in business decision-making //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2023. – Т. 21. – С. 1-4.
11. Рашидов У., Рашидов А. Роль и значение нотариальных методов в регулировании экономики //Вопросы усиления позиций Узбекистана в международной торговле и оптимизации его интеграции в мировой рынок в условиях глобальной трансформации. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 53-58.
12. Sadullaevna U. V. The role of HEMIS in the management of the educational system of higher education institutions //Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. – 2023. – Т. 20. – С. 19-22.
13. Убайдуллаева В. Digitization-an important "Driver" of the development of New Uzbekistan //Информатика и инженерные технологии. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 173-176.
14. Ubaydullaeva V. UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM TIZIMIDA TA'LIMNING TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO 'LLASH MUAMMOLARI //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 132-143.
15. Ubaydullayeva V., Bozorboyev D. YAPONIYA IQTISODIY MO 'JIZASI VA UNING OQIBATLARI //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 26-32.
16. Убайдуллаева В. С. ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИ ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИНИ БОШҚАРИШДА НЕМИШНИНГ РОЛИ //Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 24-29.

17. Shahzod M. O‘ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – C. 153-156.
18. Mansurov S., Mamatov F., Fazliddin M. COMPARISON OF THE CONCEPTS OF THE BUSINESS SEGMENT AND THE CENTER OF RESPONSIBILITY USED IN THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF RETAIL ENTERPRISES //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 203-208.
19. Dostonbek K. SPIRITUAL AND MORAL ENVIRONMENT OF SOCIETY //Social science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 128-133.
20. Mansurov S., Kochimova S., Mukhtorov F. THE FINANCIAL STRATEGY OF THE ORGANIZATION AS A FACTOR OF ENSURING ECONOMIC SECURITY IN THE LONG TERM //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 209-213.
21. Mansurov S. O ‘ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTI BO ‘YICHA PROGNOZLAR //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 3. – C. 187-195.
22. Kamolov D. Davlat boshqaruviga oid axloqiy qarashlar //Адабиёт учкунлари. – 2021.
23. Usmanova V. INCREASING INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY //International Journal of Advance Scientific Research. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 05. – C. 131-138.
24. Shahzod M. O‘ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – C. 153-156.
25. Sardor B., Ibragimovich T. K. Digital Transformation Directions in the Restaurant Business //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 1-4.
26. Kamolov D. JAMIYATNING MA’NAVYIY-AXLOQIY MUHITI //Social science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 78-82.
27. Bo‘ltakov S. et al. TURIZM SOHASIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI AHAMIYATI //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 60-62.
28. Bo‘ltakov S., Axrorov S. PULNING PAYDO BO ‘LISHI VA XUSUSIYATLARI //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 97-101.
29. Bultakov S., Bozorboyev D. O ‘ZBEKISTONDA RAQOBATCHILIK MUHITINING VUJUDGA KELISHI VA RAQOBAT TO ‘G ‘RISIDAGI QONUNCHILIKNING MAZMUNI VA MOHIYATI //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 73-78.
30. Kamolov, D., & Karimqulova, O. (2023). ANALYSIS OF THE ACTIVITIES OF INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC ORGANIZATIONS. *Science technology&Digital Finance*, 1(4), 199-202. <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf/article/view/kdko>
31. Bo‘ltakov S. XIZMAT KO ‘RSATISH KORXONLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 10-20.
32. Norkuziyev A. R. Theoretical Analysis Of Role Infrastructure On The Development Smes In Uzbekistan //International Conference Dedicated To The Role And Importance Of Innovative Education In The 21st Century. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 131-135.
33. Rustamovich N. A., Odil o‘g‘li K. X. O ‘ZBEKISTON HUDUDLARIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XITOIY VA TURKIYA MAMLAKATLARIDAGI OLINGAN TAJRIBALARDAN INNOVATSION USULDA FOYDALANISH //Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования. – 2023. – T. 9. – №. 2. – C. 3-11.
34. Narkuziyev A., Norbekova M. KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INFRATUZILMA FAOLIYATIDAN FOYDALANISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 3. – C. 171-186.
35. Наркузиев А. Р. ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ПОНЯТИЯ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ КАК ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ КАТЕГОРИИ И ЕЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В СФЕРЕ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА //PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 21. – C. 11-14.

36. Narkuziyev A. R. ICHKI RESURSLARGA ASOSLANGAN HUDUDIY INFRATUZILMANI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASINI QO „LLASH (O „ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK SOHASI UCHUN FOYDALANISH IMKOMIYATLARI) //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. TSTU Conference 2. – C. 390-400.
37. Muxtarov B. QOVUNDAN MARMELAD OLIH TEXNOLOGIYASINI O ‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 3. – C. 161-170.
38. Kamolov, D., & Kilicheva, R. (2023). CONFUCIAN AND LEGIST DOCTRINE. *Science technology&Digital Finance*, 1(4), 187-192. <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf/article/view/drrkk>
39. Botir M., Nodirbek X. QO‘SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG‘INING AHOLI DAROMADLARIGA TA‘SIRI //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – C. 253-257.
40. Botir M. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O ‘TISH DAVRIDA YUZAGA KELAYOTGAN MUAMMOLAR //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – C. 257-260.
41. Mukhtarov B. A. et al. Manifestation of Corruption in Society //Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 14. – C. 156-166.
42. Мухтаров Б. Ozbekiston respublikasida axoli daromadlarini osish dinamikasi //Современные инновационные исследования актуальные проблемы и развитие тенденции: решения и перспективы. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 579-581.
43. Соловарова М. А. ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СЕТИ ОТЕЛЕЙ MARRIOTT //Казанский вестник молодых учёных. – 2022. – Т. 6. – №. 3. – С. 98-103.
44. Sirlibekov K. PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science technology&Digital Finance*, 1 (3), 123-131. – 2023.
45. Sirlibekov K. EVENT TOURISM CENTERS OF SPAIN //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 161-167.
46. Сирлибеков Х. Ш. Факторы и особенности реализации концепции оздоровительного туризма (СПА-туризма) в современной России //Казанский вестник молодых учёных. – 2023. – Т. 6. – №. 3. – С. 98-103.
47. Kamolov D. R. O. G. L. O‘ZBEKISTONDA DEMOKRATIYA VA AXLOQNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. NUU Conference 2. – C. 348-352.
48. Usmonova V., Esanov H. THE EXISTING INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT IN THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Science technology&Digital Finance*, 1 (4), 31-40. – 2023.
49. Камолов Д. Spiritual and moral environment of society //Информатика и инженерные технологии. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 278-282.
50. Spanov M., Kamolov D. MODERN PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF DEMOCRACY AND MORALITY IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science technology&Digital Finance*, 1 (4), 168-172. – 2023.
51. Усмонова В. ХУДУДЛАРДА ИНВЕСТИЦИЯЛАР САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ //Economics and education. – 2022. – Т. 23. – №. 6. – С. 70-74.
52. Усмонова В. Б. ХУДУДЛАР ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА РАҚАМЛИ ИҚТИСОДИЁТ РИВОЖЛАНИШИНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //Current Issues of Bio Economics and Digitalization in the Sustainable Development of Regions (Germany). – 2022. – C. 139-143.